

Additional File 7. Flow cytometry dot plots of circulating Tr1 cells in two kidney transplant recipients under active immunosuppression. Percentages of Tr1 cells (CD49b⁺LAG3⁺) are shown pre- and post-transplantation. Gating was performed on live CD3⁺CD4⁺CD45RA⁻ cells.